

Traditional duck rearing practices in Assam: socio-economic contributions, challenges and sustainable approaches

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Abstract

Duck farming in Assam is rooted in traditional methods, which have been practiced by rural communities for centuries. Duck rearing in Assam predominantly follows semi-intensive and extensive systems, reflecting a reliance on natural ecosystems and minimal input costs. Extensive systems, adopted by 98% of farmers, allow ducks to forage in natural water bodies, such as ponds and paddy fields, reducing feed expenses. Flock sizes typically range from 12 to 35 ducks with a sex ratio of 1:7, although larger flocks face challenges such as limited market demand and disease outbreaks. Women play a significant role with 98% of duck farmers being women, predominantly aged 26–35 contributing to household income through duck meat, egg production, and breeding activities. Traditional practices, including the use of laying hens for egg incubation and indigenous medicinal remedies, highlight the socio-economic and cultural aspects of duck farming. Farmers use plants like neem, turmeric, holy basil, and ginger to manage duck health, leveraging their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. Duck meat and eggs serving as important income sources, especially during festive seasons. Traditional dishes like duck meat with ash gourd are culturally significant. Despite these benefits, challenges such as limited access to veterinary care, lack of artificial incubators and low awareness of advanced practices constrain the sector's growth. Promoting modern rearing techniques alongside traditional practices can enhance productivity, income, and sustainability while preserving Assam's rich heritage of duck farming.

Keywords: Assam, duck farming, indigenous medicine, sustainable livestock, traditional rearing.

Introduction

Duck farming is an integral part of rural livelihoods in Assam, especially in low-lying, flood-prone areas where ducks are more suitable than chickens. Traditional duck-rearing methods in Assam are primarily semi-intensive or extensive, allowing ducks to forage freely. Indigenous medicinal practices are commonly employed by farmers to treat duck diseases, leveraging local plant-based remedies that are economical and readily available. This traditional knowledge contributes to sustainable duck farming, aligning with the cultural heritage and ecological dynamics of the region.

According to the 20th Livestock Census (2019) conducted in India, Assam reported a duck population of approximately 6.6 million, making it stand in second position in the country (Dutta *et al* 2022). This figure represented a notable increase (20th Livestock Census, 2019) from previous years, reflecting the rising interest in duck farming in rural areas. Duck farming in Assam is particularly concentrated in areas with abundant water resources, such as the floodplains of the Brahmaputra and Barak valleys.

The most commonly reared duck in Assam is the Pati duck, the first recognized native duck breed in the country (Islam *et al.*, 2024). Other indigenous breeds like the Chara, Chemballi, Khaki Campbell, Nageswari duck, ceena duck, kersasia (Mukhi, 2019) and White Pekin ducks are also raised in these regions, benefiting from natural feeding habitats and traditional knowledge (TK) passed down through generations. However, the census also highlighted challenges, such as periodic declines in population due to diseases, including avian influenza, which have impacted the state's duck rearing economy.

There are scanty reports available regarding involvement of farmers in duck rearing in Assam. In order to preserve indigenous knowledge, support sustainable agriculture, and foster economic development among rural communities, it is imperative that Assamese duck rearing

practices be documented. Duck farming has a deep-rooted cultural and economic significance in the state, particularly in the flood-prone Brahmaputra Valley, where it serves as a critical livelihood for small-scale farmers. Documentation of these systems helps preserve traditional practices, providing insights into locally adapted breeds, feeding techniques, and eco-friendly pest control methods, which contribute to the region's biodiversity. By recording disease management practices and biosecurity measures, documentation also supports healthier flocks, reducing economic losses from diseases. Furthermore, proper records offer a foundation for understanding the economic impact of duck rearing, allowing policymakers to design better support programs and training for farmers. Documented breeding and genetic data help in conserving indigenous breeds like the Desi duck, promoting selective breeding to improve productivity and resilience. This information can be crucial for research, offering data on nutrition, breeding practices, and technological advancements that can make duck farming more efficient and profitable. Detailed documentation also enhances market access by promoting the quality and nutritional benefits of duck products, enabling farmers to explore value-added products like processed meat and eggs. It not only supports rural livelihoods but also strengthens food security and paves the way for sustainable agricultural practices. Overall, comprehensive documentation of duck rearing in Assam holds immense potential to benefit local farmers, protect environmental health, and contribute to a more resilient agricultural economy in the state.

Therefore the study was undertaken to know the socio-economic characteristics of duck farmers, to know the traditional management and rearing system followed in duck farming, to find out the available traditional medicine used for treatment of duck, to identify the constraints faced by the

farmers and lastly to find out the annual income obtained from duck farming.

Materials and methods

According to the 20th Livestock Census of Assam, conducted in 2019, Lakhimpur district has a significant duck population, reflecting the region's reliance on duck farming as a source of livelihood, especially in rural and flood-prone areas. Duck rearing is integral to the local agricultural system in Lakhimpur due to its resilience in waterlogged areas and its role in sustaining the rural economy. In the 20th Livestock Census, Lakhimpur recorded a duck population of approximately 230,000 ducks. Therefore, the study was conducted in Lakhimpur district under North bank plain zone of Assam in August, September and October months of 2023. Farmers who were involved actively in duck rearing chosen as the respondent for the study. ITKs were documented through interaction and discussion with farmers of the study area. Respondents were interviewed on various identified parameters through an interview schedule to assess the status and success of duck farming, the income generation in a year. For the purpose a total of five hundred members of respondents were selected and interviewed with a standard questionnaire. Information on locally available plants, herbs and other natural resources used to manage and prevent common ailments of duck were collected.

Health status of the duck was accessed through haematological evaluation for different parameters. Blood samples were collected from the wing vein of 150 clinically healthy adult ducks (aged 1-2 years), using EDTA as an anticoagulant. Avian hematological techniques, as described by Coles and Campbell (1986), were employed to determine total erythrocyte count, total leukocyte count, hemoglobin concentration, hematocrit value, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration

(MCHC) and thrombocyte count. Differential leukocyte counts were performed on blood smears stained with Wright's stain, following the method outlined by Jain (1986).

Result and discussions

1. Traditional Rearing System of Ducks in Assam

This substantial population is a testament to the district's reliance on traditional, semi-intensive and extensive duck-rearing practices. In the study it was observed that 98% farmers (Table 1) reared in extensive system of rearing. The ducks are primarily reared in extensive systems, where they forage in natural water bodies, including ponds, rivers, and paddy fields. This method of rearing reduces feeding costs, as ducks find food naturally available in these habitats, such as aquatic plants, insects, and small fish.

The flock size observed in the survey areas ranged from 10 to 120 ducks with a male:female ratio of 1:5 to 1:8, however majority of the farmers maintained a sex ratio of 1:7. In almost all the study areas farmers usually keep small flocks (12-35) of ducks. Similar observation of small flock sizes were reported by Dutta *et al.*, 2024 in Morigaon district of Assam. Most of the farmers are interested to keep smaller sized duck flock mainly due to lack of market, since they cannot sell large numbers of duck at a time and other reason being the outbreak of diseases, which kills their ducks from time to time. It was observed that some of the farmers incubated their duck eggs using laying hens, as according to them ducks are inefficient in incubating and hatching out of their young ones. Majority of the duck in the region hatched eggs during April to July months of the year. There was no record of using artificial incubator in the region, which was due to lack of awareness, scientific knowledge and sufficient fund to procure artificial incubator. For incubation of eggs, the farmers provide boxes prepared from bamboo (Figure 1a and 1b). The hens rest over the eggs within the bamboo boxes for incubation. In both extensive and semi-

intensive system of duck rearing farmers facilitate drinking and feeding of ducklings inside an enclosed premise, which were mainly made of bamboo or fish nets. Ducklings were not allowed to swim up to 12-18 days of age and after about one month of age, ducks are let loose (free range system) to the nearby ponds and water bodies, then after no extra feeds are provided. There was no record of any vaccination of the ducks in the studied region. On the contrary, duck farmers from Kerala and West Bengal usually does regular vaccination and follows standard management practices (Leung, 2014).

1.1 Extensive Rearing System

The extensive rearing system is the most prevalent form of duck farming in the area of study. In this system, ducks are reared in natural water bodies like ponds (Figure 2 a), paddy fields, and wetlands (Figure 2 b), where they forage for food, including aquatic plants, insects, snails, and small fish. The extensive system is primarily

practiced during the rainy season, when water resources are abundant and ducks can freely forage in the flooded fields (Zamanet *al.*, 2005). This system minimizes feed costs and is considered environmentally sustainable, as it integrates ducks into the natural ecosystem without additional feed or infrastructure investment.

1.2 Semi-Intensive System

In some areas, farmers practice a semi-intensive system (0.06%), which combines free-ranging with limited confinement (Figure 3a, 3b,3c). Ducks are often provided a night shelter but are allowed to roam freely during the day. This system is particularly beneficial during the dry season when natural water bodies may shrink, limiting forage availability (Jai Sunderet *al.*, 2005). Farmers often supplement ducks' diets with rice bran, kitchen waste, and broken rice, reducing dependency on commercial feeds and lowering costs.

Table 1. Rearing System of Duck

Extensive Rearing System	Semi-Intensive System	Intensive System
465/500=93%	30/500=0.06%	05/500=0.01%

2. Involvement of Women in Duck Rearing

It was recorded that women (Figure 4a, 4b) play a significant role in duck rearing in Assam. It was observed in the experiment that 98% of duck rearing farmers were women with different socio-economic characteristic (Table 2). They are responsible for feeding, healthcare and sometimes even shelter construction, indicating the gendered division of labor in traditional farming. This involvement has implications for women's empowerment and household economic stability, as duck rearing contributes significantly to rural incomes (Naik *et al.* 2022). The majority (47.20%) of married women in the age group of 26-35 were involved in duck farming were followed other age groups (Table 2). Most of the ducks were reared for commercial meat purpose followed by duckling and egg production (Table 2).

Table 2 Socio-economic characteristic of women participants in duck farming

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age group (years)		
Upto 25	122/500	24.40
26-35	208	41.60
36-45	134	26.80
46 & above	113	22.60
Marital status		
Single	166	33.20

Married	236	47.20
Widow	175	35.0
Years of experience		
1-10	112	22.4
11-20	132	26.40
21-30	253	50.60
>30	80	16.00
Reason for keeping		
House hold Consumption	136	27.20
Commercial	Fattening	283
	Breeding	158
	Egg production	350
		0.70

3. Traditional Medicinal Practices for Ducks

In the study, the majority of duck farmers are aware of the main health issues that their ducks face, which include paralysis, circular movement before death, and greenish white watery diarrhoea in ducklings. Farmers inquire about their preventive measures. In most of the cases farmers were found to use alternative measures instead of conventional veterinary practices mainly due to lack of awareness and lack of veterinary services at farmers' doorstep and unavailability of veterinary drugs and vaccines at their localities. Traditional medicinal practices for ducks in Assam involve using locally available plants, herbs and other natural resources to manage and prevent common ailments. These remedies are passed down through generations, representing an important aspect of indigenous knowledge on medicinal practices and herbs.

3.1 Commonly Used Medicinal Plants

Extract of many plants and herbs contain bio-active components with anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial (Hammer *et al.*, 1999), antioxidant (Hashemi and SR, 2010), and anthelmintic properties. Some commonly used plants in traditional duck medicine in Assam include neem (*Azadirachta indica*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), holy basil (*Ocimum sanctum*) and Moringa leaves (Table 3). These plants have antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, making them effective in managing common health issues in ducks (Gogoi and Nath, 2021).

- **Neem** (*Azadirachta indica*): Neem leaves are often crushed in to paste and added to duck drinking water to prevent bacterial infections. Subapriya and Nagini, (2005) demonstrated the great anthelmintic efficacy of neem extract in Aseel chicken.
- **Turmeric**: Farmers mix turmeric powder with feed to improve immunity and prevent respiratory infections. The turmeric in the form of paste was mostly used to treat wound, skin infection, and joint ill. The major bio-active compound is the curcumin, a phenolic molecule that has been demonstrated to have immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities (Allen *et al.*, 1997).
- **Holy Basil**: Basil leaves are crushed and mixed with water or feed to help control digestive disorders.
- **Use of green chili paste and black pepper** was practiced by some farmer to relief pain due to external injury.
- **Akashi lota** (*Cuscuta reflexa*) was traditionally used as anthelmintic in ducks.

- ***Moringaoleifera* Lam:** Some farmers feed leaves of *Moringaoleifera* leaves in paste form along with feeds believing that the plants decrease parasite infestation and improve weight gain in poultry.
- **Ginger (*Zingiberofficinale*):** Some duck farmer's feeds ginger leaves after their harvest believing that ginger enhances digestive activity and enhanced growth and weight gain. Feeding of diet supplemented with ginger at a concentration of 125 mg/kg in quails showed better feed conversion ratio, body weight, and humoral immunity compared to normal feed. (Ullah *et al.*, 2024).
- ***Xylorrhya autumnalis* (locally known as *khutura*):** In about 5% of the study area, farmers fed their duckling with raw flower of the locally available *khutura* herb up to 4-5 days. They believe that feeding this helps to achieve faster body weight. Though such scientific data are not available but can be a base of research. Feeding of *khutura* flower to ducklings has been reported in Nagaon district of Assam (Islam *et al.*, 2002).

Table 3. Traditional plants used in management and prevention of common ailments in duck.

Species	Family	Vernacular name	Illness treated	Plant parts used and methods for making medication
<i>Colocasia esculenta</i>	Araceae	Kola Kachu	Minor injury	Leaves and roots. Leaves were grind and prepared paste. It possess blood coagulation property and useful for management of minor injury. Roots were used as feed supplement after boiling it.
<i>Erechthites valerianaefolia</i> DC	Compositae	Bon Kopah	Cut wounds	Leaves, Juice from the leaves is used in for quickhealing.
<i>Solanum indicum</i> Linn.	Solanaceae	Tit Bhekuri	Skin diseases	Glue prepared from the roots is used in skin diseases.
<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> Linn.	Compositae	Chirota	Anthelmintics and respiratory dysfunctions.	Leaf juice is used as anthelmintics and respiratory dysfunctions.
<i>Zingiberofficinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Ada	Rhizome	Respiratory dysfunctions.
<i>Gymnopetalum Cochinchinense</i>	Cucurbiaceae	Kauri kerala	Root	Root paste are used as analgesic and in respiratory dysfunctions
<i>Hibiscus subdariffa</i> Linn.	Malvaceae	Mesta tenga/ Tengamora	Fruit	Used in treatment of severe diarrhea with blood or mucus.
<i>Garcinia lanceifolia</i>	Clusiaceae	Rupohi-thekeera	Fruit	Treatment of gastr intestinal disorder.
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (Linn.)	Lamiaceae	Tulsi	Leaves, Seeds	Leaf/ seed juice is used as insect Repellant in duck shelter houses.

3.2 Application Techniques

Traditional medicinal practices involve simple preparation techniques. For instance, neem leaves are soaked in water overnight, and the water is then provided to ducks as a preventive measure against infections or prepare paste from the leaves and mix with drinking water. Similarly, turmeric

powder is mixed with feed to act as an immune booster. These methods are cost-effective and easy to apply, making them accessible to rural farmers with limited resources.

3.3 Efficacy and Limitations

While traditional medicine has been beneficial, there are limitations in terms of efficacy and consistency. The lack of standardized dosages

and potential side effects of some herbal remedies are challenges that need addressing. However, these practices remain popular due to the limited availability and high cost of veterinary medicines (Islam *et al.* 2023). The conventional methods of raising ducks and treating illnesses are both environment friendly and economically feasible. By reducing dependence on commercial feed and synthetic medicines, these methods promote eco-friendly practices. Duck farming also provides an additional income source, reducing poverty and enhancing food security among rural households (Islam *et al.*, 2019).

3.4 Economic importance of duck

In almost all the places of Assam, duck meat along with ash gourd (*Benincasahispida*) occupies a special place in traditional ethnic Assamese dish. Most the Assamese people have preference of the indigenous Pati breed of duck instead of other duck breed for their Assamese cuisine. Same kind of preference pattern was observed in the present study. Duck farmers usually procure day old to one month age duckling from near-by local markets, neighbour and near-by duck farmers. The price of duckling varies depending upon the age and quality of ducklings. The prices of duckling in the present study area varied from Rs.50-60/duckling and it reach up to Rs. 100/- at one month of age. The study showed that the ducks were reared both for egg and meat purpose. However, the demand for duck meat was much higher compared to egg in the study area. The demand and consumption of duck meat increases many folds during festive seasons like new year eve, Maghbihu (A harvest festival of Assam, celebrated between 13-15th January of the year) etc. Duck egg is being sold at Rs.20-30/egg. And the selling price of an adult duck varies from Rs. 500-700 per duck. The duck meat consumers under the study site preferred to consume duck meat from November to January/February. Ducks are believed to be tastier and full of flavour due to more fat deposition and fully matured during this period. Under the

present study duck farming was found to be a subsidiary income source for all the farmers since ducks were kept besides other livestock like cattle, goat, pig, backyard poultry and agriculture.

4. Hematological parameters of duck.

The mean values of total RBC count corresponds with the values of Indian ducks (Sturkie and Griminger 1986) and Nigerian local duck Olayemi *et al* 2002. The hemoglobin values recorded in the study was lower than other ducks reported by Kocane and Martel Pitts (1976) and this might be due to lower body size (Ghadiri-Anari *et al* 2014) in the breeds of duck reared in Assam. The values recorded (Table 4) for other parameters in the present study were in accordance with the hematological values observed by Bhattacharyya *et al.* (1991), Tadjalli *et al* (1996) and Jain A and Shakkarpude, 2022.

Parameters	
RBC (millions/ μ l)	2.74 \pm 0.16
PCV (%)	42.15 \pm 5.11
Hb (g/dl)	14.72 \pm 27.1
WBC (thousands/ul)	7.1 \pm 0.43
MCH (pg)	55.32 \pm 77.15
MCHC (g/dl)	36.79 \pm 3.99
MCV (fl)	161.11 \pm 15.92
Lymphocyte (%)	47.10 \pm 1.1
Heterophil (%)	45.29 \pm 1.37
Monocyte (%)	7.12 \pm 1.27
Eosinophil (%)	3.92 \pm 0.45
Basophil (%)	2.12 \pm 0.37

Table 4: Haematological value for duck

Conclusion:

The growth (20th Livestock Census, 2019) of duck farming in Lakhimpur can be attributed to the increased adoption of traditional knowledge regarding local duck breeds and medicinal practices, which aid in disease management and health maintenance. Duck rearing in the district not only provides a livelihood to smallholder farmers but also enhances food security through the provision of eggs and meat. The traditional rearing system of ducks in Assam, complemented

by indigenous medicinal practices, is a reflection of the community's rich cultural heritage and deep connection with nature. These practices offer a sustainable model for small-scale farming that benefits both the environment and rural livelihoods. However, integrating modern scientific research with traditional knowledge could enhance the efficacy and safety of these practices, potentially providing a blueprint for sustainable poultry farming across similar regions.

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Figure 1.a.
Box prepared from bamboo used for incubation of eggs.

Figure 1.b.

Figure 2.a.
Extensive Rearing System

Figure 2.b.

Figure 3a: Semi-Intensive/ intensive System

Figure 3b Semi-Intensive/ intensive System

Figure, 3c Semi-Intensive/ intensive System

Figure 4a
Involvement of Women in Duck Rearing

Figure 4b